

MEDICAL AND HYGIENIC EDUCATION AND TRAINING OF THE POPULATION AND THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract. *Medical and hygienic education is a part of the state healthcare system, including the dissemination of medical and hygienic knowledge, the formation of a healthy lifestyle (HLS) and the instillation of hygienic skills in the population in order to maintain and strengthen health, increase efficiency and active longevity.*

Key words: *healthy lifestyle, hygiene, population, risk factors, epidemiology. The main goal of medical and hygienic education of the population is the formation of knowledge and skills to independently make decisions on issues of maintaining and strengthening health.*

МЕДИКО-ГИГИЕНИЧЕСКОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И ВОСПИТАНИЕ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ И ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ

Аннотация. *Медико-гигиеническое образование — часть государственной системы здравоохранения, включающая распространение медико-гигиенических знаний, формирование здорового образа жизни (ЗОЖ) и привитие гигиенических навыков населению в целях сохранения и укрепления здоровья, повышения работоспособности и активного долголетия.*

Ключевые слова: *здоровый образ жизни, гигиена, население, факторы риска, эпидемиология. Основной целью медико-гигиенического образования населения является формирование знаний и умений самостоятельно принимать решения по вопросам сохранения и укрепления здоровья.*

There is a pressing need to transform knowledge about a healthy lifestyle into skills.

When determining the direction of this work, we should talk not about health education, but about hygienic education and training. A relevant component of medical and social activity is the attitude towards a healthy lifestyle. Training means the development of skills and abilities as prerequisites for proper hygienic behavior. Education is the development of beliefs, views, character traits as the acting force of this behavior. The result of medical and hygienic training and education of the population is the improvement of public health, increase of sanitary and epidemiological well-being of the region, correction of the main risk factors of diseases.

The main tasks in the formation of a healthy lifestyle and medical and hygienic training and education of the population are:

- promotion of a healthy lifestyle;

- formation of a healthy lifestyle ideology among the population, strengthening of the physical and spiritual health of the population;
- development of health-saving technologies;
- conducting applied scientific and epidemiological research to substantiate the improvement of legislation and the methodological base;
- ensuring interdepartmental cooperation and functioning of the coordination mechanism;
- development of modern approaches and provision of conditions for training specialists, improvement of curricula, development of the infrastructure of scientific and educational institutions;
- organization and development of medical and preventive care by introducing modern medical and preventive technologies;
- organizational and methodological support for the activities of regional preventive organizations (medical prevention centers), as well as primary health care organizations (PHC);
- development and implementation of national information and communication campaigns;
- organization of vertical interaction between medical prevention centers and prevention offices in primary care;
- organization of health schools based on the main risk factors;
- development of conditions for maintaining a healthy lifestyle, including ensuring monitoring and a modern level of control (supervision) over the compliance of products intended for humans, as well as factors of the human environment with the requirements of current legislation.

Increasing the level of medical activity and literacy of the population is the most important task of a district physician, pediatrician and especially a general practitioner.

Principles of medical and hygienic training and education of the population:

1. State character - the state finances the activities of institutions and organizations for hygienic training and education of the population, ensures the development of the material and technical base, personnel training, and the legal basis for the activities of service institutions.
2. Scientific nature - compliance of medical and hygienic knowledge with the current state of science and practice.
3. Mass character - participation of all medical workers, involvement of specialists from other departments and public organizations.
4. Accessibility - when presenting the material, it is necessary to avoid obscure medical terms, the speech should be easy to understand.

5. Purposefulness - the work should be carried out in a chosen direction in a differentiated manner, taking into account various groups of the population.

6. Optimism - to achieve the effect, it is important to emphasize the possibility of successfully combating diseases.

7. Relevance - the choice of the direction of work should be relevant at the given moment in time.

The main areas of formation of the medical and hygienic culture of the population include the formation of healthy lifestyle skills in the younger generation, deepening and consolidating hygienic knowledge and beliefs, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among the population, the development of sanitary and hygienic activity and amateur activities to assist health authorities.

For more effective informing of the population, hygienic training and education is carried out in various target groups:

- by age composition (children in kindergarten, schoolchildren and pupils, students, etc.);
- social status (working, pensioners);
- professional characteristics (industrial workers, decreed groups of the population, security service workers, etc.); - the presence of diseases (arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, gastrointestinal diseases, etc.).

Formation of target groups is advisable, since similar forms and methods of preventive interventions are used: for example, specialized schools for patients with diabetes, arterial hypertension, etc. Information is presented taking into account age, level of education, presence of certain risk factors. When working with the population at all levels, information is presented in an accessible way for the general population, without using complex medical terms, and is of a positive nature.

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